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Impact Of Boko Haram Insurgence On Western Education In Some Selected Local Government Areas In Yobe State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on western education in some selected Local Government Areas in Yobe State, Nigeria. The researchers used survey research design for the study while the purposive and random sampling techniques were utilized to determine the sample for the study. A sample of 198 respondents was used and primary information was obtained by the use of a structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview from the selected Local Government Areas of the state. The data collected were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The probability value of the regression analysis estimate was used in testing the hypotheses of the study. The result of the regression analysis indicates that Boko Haram insurgency has positive impact on western education in Yobe State, Nigeria and the relationship is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The relationship is in line with a priori expectation. It was concluded that Boko Haram insurgency has profoundly devastated and disrupted the educational landscape in Yobe State, particularly in the selected Local Government Areas, leading to a cyclical reinforcement between insecurity and educational challenges. This implies that the insurgency and educational challenges in Yobe State are mutually reinforcing. This interplay exacerbates the state's socio-economic instability and hinders development. It was recommended that government in collaboration with humanitarian partners and policymakers should incorporate guidelines that prioritize infrastructure reconstruction, improved working conditions, sustained investment in non-formal learning centers and community-based education initiatives, digitize and automate data collection, public sensitization campaigns on the value of education and enhanced security as viable solutions to address the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency in Yobe State.

Keywords: Boko Haram, Development, Educational challenges, Insurgency, Reinforcement.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria has struggled with addressing the Boko Haram insurgency, with the government implementing various strategies to counter the group's activities. However, challenges persist, including the protection

of educational institutions and the rehabilitation of affected regions. Narrowing down to area of the study, Yobe State, situated in north-eastern region, has been one of the epicenters of Boko Haram activities. The state has faced severe disruptions to its education system, with many schools attacked, students abducted, and teachers killed (Onuoha, 2015). The impact on Western education in Yobe State is profound, with a significant number of students unable to pursue education as a result of the continuing conflict. The destruction of educational infrastructure and the displacement of communities further exacerbate the challenges faced by the state. As earlier mentioned, one distinctive feature of Boko Haram's strategy is its targeting of educational institutions. Schools in Yobe State have witnessed numerous attacks, including the 2014 Chibok schoolgirls kidnapping in neighboring Borno State. This deliberate assault education reflects the group's ideology, with the name "Boko Haram" translating to "Western education is forbidden".

The insurgency has led to a humanitarian crisis in Yobe State, with widespread displacement, food insecurity, and a significant impact on the overall well-being of the population. The prolonged conflict has strained resources and hindered efforts to rebuild affected communities (Dambazau, 2016, p.756). The Nigerian government has undertaken various counterterrorism measures to address the Boko Haram threat in Nigeria, including Yobe State. Military interventions, emergency rule declarations, and collaboration with international partners have been part of the response, although challenges persist in fully eradicating the insurgency. As of the latest available information, Boko Haram's activities in Yobe State continue to pose challenges to security and development. Efforts to address the root causes of the insurgency, rebuild infrastructure, and rehabilitate affected communities is still ongoing (International Crisis Group, 2021). Studies show that education plays a vital role in promoting stability and peace in conflict affected societies. As De Grauwe, Rostan, and Rodgers (2017) suggest, access to quality education provides an alternative path for young people, reduce their vulnerability to being coerced or enticed into armed conflict. Education empowers communities affected by conflict by equipping individuals with the skills and knowledge necessary for personal and collective development. Education fosters resilience and agency, enabling individuals to actively contribute to rebuilding their communities. Post-conflict societies benefit from education as a tool for fostering reconciliation and understanding. Staub (2011) emphasizes the role of education in promoting empathy, reducing prejudice, and building bridges between different ethnic, religious, or cultural groups. Education is a fundamental driver of human capital and economic development. UNESCO (2021) emphasizes the long-term benefits of education in conflict zones, and its role in breaking the cycle of poverty and contributes to sustainable development. Against this background, this study seeks to empirically examine the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on Western education in Yobe State, with a focus on understanding the challenges faced by the education system in the aftermath of the insurgency.

Statement of the Problem

The persistent insurgency orchestrated by Boko Haram in Yobe State has precipitated a profound and multi-faceted crisis within the Western education sector. The deleterious consequences of this conflict are palpable and extend beyond the immediate acts of violence, manifesting in systematic disruptions that weaken the very foundation of educational structures and opportunities for the youth. As it is confronted with the gravity of this issue, it becomes imperative to articulate the specific challenges that define the landscape of Western education in Yobe State within the context of the Boko Haram insurgency. The series of targeted attacks on educational institutions by Boko Haram has resulted in a considerable loss of educational infrastructure, rendering schools dysfunctional and impeding the continuity of Western education. The abduction of students by Boko Haram represents a grievous affront to the sanctity of education. The infamous incidents, akin to the Chibok schoolgirls' kidnapping, have not only scarred the affected students but have also sown seeds of fear and mistrust among parents and communities. The displacement of communities due to the insurgency further exacerbates the challenges faced by Western education in Yobe State. While these challenges are apparent, a comprehensive understanding of the impact of Boko Haram on Western education in Yobe State necessitates an empirical examination. An evidence-based approach is crucial for discerning the nuanced dynamics, identifying the most pressing issues, and formulating effective interventions. This study seeks to unravel the intricate layers of the

crisis, providing invaluable insights that can inform policies, strategies, and initiatives aimed at restoring and fortifying Western education in the wake of the Boko Haram insurgency.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to empirically examine the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on Western education in Yobe State, with a focus on understanding the challenges faced by the education system in the aftermath of the insurgency. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To assess the impact of Boko Haram's insurgency on the infrastructure of secondary schools in Yobe State.
2. To examine the effect of the abduction of students on enrolment and attendance rates in secondary schools in Yobe State.
3. To examine the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on access to quality secondary education in displaced communities, with a focus on the availability and retention of qualified teaching personnel in Yobe State.
4. To explore the coping strategies adopted by secondary schools and communities to address educational challenges arising from the insurgency.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute valuable insights and inform policies aimed at addressing the challenges faced by western education in Yobe State in the aftermath of the Boko Haram insurgency.

1. Policymakers and government officials at both the state and national levels will gain valuable insights into the specific issues affecting western education in Yobe State.
2. The study's insights will aid in crafting more effective management approaches, ensuring that schools in Yobe State can provide a conducive and secure learning environment for students and teachers.
3. Teachers will gain a clearer picture of the challenges they face in the aftermath of insurgency, enabling them to adapt their teaching methods and support mechanisms to address the specific needs of students.
4. Students and their parents will benefit from improved educational conditions, as the study's recommendations will lead to targeted interventions, such as counselling services or infrastructure improvements that enhance the overall educational experience.
5. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and humanitarian agencies operating in the region will find the study instrumental in guiding their interventions.
6. Finally, the broader academic community and researchers focusing on conflict studies, education, and social development will benefit from the study's insights. The research will add to the existing body of knowledge on the intersection of conflict and education, providing a case study that can inform future research endeavours. The study's methodology and findings will serve as a reference for scholars seeking to explore the multifaceted impacts of conflict on educational systems.

Scope of the Study

This study covered the effects of Boko Haram Insurgency in Yobe state on the educational development in the state; twenty-seven (27) schools were selected from the areas affected randomly. The study examines the relationship between the two variables Boko Haram insurgency and its impact on educational development. This research focused on secondary schools, excluding primary schools due to children's comprehension levels and Boko Haram's activities, and omitted tertiary institutions to emphasize post-primary education, where early de-radicalization can foster an educated citizenry. This research is limited to issues bordering on Boko Haram conflict and the challenge of western education in Yobe state.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following research questions:

1. How has the Boko Haram insurgency affected the infrastructure of secondary schools in Yobe State?

2. What impact has the abduction of students by Boko Haram had on the enrolment and attendance rates in secondary schools in Yobe State?
3. How has the Boko Haram insurgency impacted access to quality secondary education in displaced communities, particularly in relation to the availability and retention of qualified teaching personnel in Yobe State?
4. What are the coping strategies employed by secondary schools and communities in Yobe State to mitigate the educational disruptions caused by Boko Haram?

Hypothesis

H0₁: Boko Haram insurgency is likely to significantly deteriorate the infrastructure of secondary schools in Yobe State.

H0₂: The abduction of students by Boko Haram is likely to lead to a significant decline in enrolment and attendance rates in secondary schools in Yobe State.

H0₃: Boko Haram insurgency is likely to impact access to quality secondary education in displaced communities by reducing the availability and retention of qualified teaching personnel in Yobe State.

H0₄: Secondary schools and communities in Yobe State are likely to develop various coping strategies, including community-based security initiatives, psychological support programmes, and alternative learning methods, to mitigate the educational disruptions caused by Boko Haram.

Conceptual Framework

Boko Haram's Origins, Ideology, and Evolution

Boko Haram, officially known as Jama'atu Ahlis Sunna Lidda'awati Wal-Jihad, emerged in the early 2000s in Maiduguri, Nigeria, under the leadership of Mohammed Yusuf (Thurston, 2018). The group's ideology is rooted in Salafi-jihadism, advocating for the rejection of Western-style education and governance, which it perceives as corrupt and incompatible with Islamic law (Zenn, 2020). Following Yusuf's death in 2009, Boko Haram evolved into a violent insurgency under Abubakar Shekau, intensifying attacks against state institutions, civilians, and educational establishments. The group later splintered, with the Islamic State West Africa Province (ISWAP) emerging as a faction in 2016 (Onuoha, 2014).

The Boko Haram's ideology and evolution have been extensively studied within the context of historical Islamic movements in Nigeria. Adesoji (2011) draws comparisons between Boko Haram and earlier fundamentalist groups like Maitatsine, emphasizing how socio-economic and political factors contributed to their rise. Similarly, Walker (2016) argues that Boko Haram's radical stance stems from deep-rooted grievances against perceived Western cultural imperialism and corrupt governance.

Boko Haram's Impact on Education

Boko Haram's insurgency has devastated Nigeria's education sector, particularly in the northeast. Between 2009 and 2021, over 1,500 schools were destroyed or closed, affecting millions of children's access to education (UNESCO, 2021). According to Human Rights Watch (2020), Boko Haram has abducted over 1,000 students, including the well-documented Chibok and Dapchi kidnappings. These attacks undermine human capital development and deepen the region's socio-economic challenges (Umar, 2021).

Displacement and Migration

The Boko Haram insurgency has displaced over 2.5 million people in the Lake Chad region, including thousands of students and teachers (UNHCR, 2021).

Challenges to Western Education

Western education in many developing countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, faces significant challenges, including inadequate infrastructure, poor funding, and security concerns. Nigeria, as the most populous African country, has struggled to ensure quality secondary education, with disparities across regions, especially in the northeast and northwest (UNESCO, 2021). Studies indicate that factors such as inadequate school facilities, poor teacher retention, and sociocultural norms contribute to the declining

enrolment and retention rates in secondary education (Eze, 2019). Furthermore, insecurity due to insurgency and banditry has led to the closure of numerous schools, further impeding educational progress (Human Rights Watch, 2021).

Interaction of Mediating Factors and Outcome Variables in Educational Challenges

The impact of insurgency on education is shaped by multiple mediating factors, including government policies, community responses, and international interventions while displacement has negatively affected education access, initiatives like UNICEF's *Educate A Child* program have mitigated some of the challenges (UNICEF, 2021). The severity of educational disruptions is also influenced by factors such as gender, socioeconomic status, and location (urban vs. rural) (UNESCO, 2021).

How Boko Haram's Insurgency and Educational Challenges Reinforce Each Other

The Boko Haram insurgency and educational challenges in Northeast Nigeria are mutually reinforcing. The insurgency has led to the destruction of educational infrastructure, displacement of students and teachers, and a climate of fear that discourages school attendance. The insurgency has profoundly disrupted the educational landscape in Northeast Nigeria, particularly in states like Yobe, leading to a cyclical reinforcement between insecurity and educational challenges. This interplay exacerbates the region's socio-economic instability and hinders development.

A significant impact of the insurgency is the widespread destruction of educational infrastructure. The deliberate targeting of educational institutions not only disrupts learning but also instills fear, discouraging attendance and leading to prolonged closures. The insurgency has also led to significant loss of life among educators and students, creating a shortage of qualified personnel and further degrading the quality of education. The displacement of communities due to Boko Haram's activities has forced many students and teachers into internally displaced persons (IDP) camps, where access to quality education is limited.

The psychological trauma inflicted by the insurgency cannot be overstated. The constant threat of violence and abduction has instilled deep fear among students and parents, leading to decreased school attendance and increased dropout rates. This environment of fear perpetuates educational challenges, as students are either too afraid to attend school or parents are reluctant to send their children, especially girls, to school. The educational setbacks caused by the insurgency contribute to a lack of economic opportunities, fostering conditions that can lead to further radicalization and recruitment into insurgent groups. This creates a vicious cycle where educational challenges and insurgency reinforce each other, perpetuating instability in the region. Addressing this intertwined crisis requires a multifaceted approach. Rebuilding and securing educational infrastructure is paramount. Providing psychological support to affected individuals, ensuring the safety of students and teachers, and implementing policies that promote inclusive and resilient education systems are crucial steps toward breaking this cycle.

Theoretical framework

Conflict Theory

Conflict theory is propounded by Karl Marx in 1885. The theory asserts that tensions and conflicts arise when resources, status, and power are unevenly distributed between groups in society and that these conflicts become the engine for social change. Conflict theory draws attention to the formation of violence happening all over the regions of Nigeria particularly northeast geo-political zone. The reason for choosing this theory is that Boko Haram claimed that they have been deprived and marginalized by the Nigerian government over the years. Conflict theory argued that group consciousness and ethnic formation is as a result of deprivation and marginalization, and this led to insurgency and violence in the northeast. Although, this study does not look at insurgency as engine for social change rather the root cause of conflict or insurgency in the broader sense.

Education for Peace building Theory

Education for Peace building is a theoretical framework that recognizes the potential of education to promote peace, prevent conflict, and contribute to the reconstruction of societies affected by violence. The theory was further developed by Dewey (1859-1952), Dewey's educational philosophy emphasizing experiential learning and the development of critical thinking skills. While not explicitly an advocate for

peace education, his ideas laid the groundwork for the integration of peace building principles into educational practices.

The key principles of the theory include among others that Education for Peace building emphasizes inclusive and equitable education that addresses the needs of diverse communities. Education for Peace building is relevant in this study of Boko Haram insurgency and the challenges of post primary education in Yobe State, especially in preventing violence and extremism by fostering values of tolerance, respect, and understanding. Education for Peace building plays a crucial role in rebuilding societies. It helps address trauma, reconcile communities, and establish a foundation for sustainable peace. By addressing root causes of conflict and promoting systemic change, Education for Peace building contributes to long-term social transformation. It creates a culture where conflicts are resolved peacefully and inclusively.

Frustration-Aggression Theory

The Frustration-Aggression Theory was originally formulated by **Dollard, Miller, Doob, Mowrer, and Sears** in their 1939 work *Frustration and Aggression*. The central idea behind the Frustration-Aggression Theory is that **frustration** (the blocking of a goal or desire) leads to **aggression**. The aggression is often directed towards those perceived to be responsible for the blockage of the goal or, in some cases, displaced onto other targets if direct aggression is not possible. The theory suggests that when individuals or groups are denied basic needs or are prevented from achieving important goals (such as socio-political, economic, or religious objectives), their frustration can manifest as aggressive behavior, often violent.

In the context of Boko Haram, the insurgent group can be seen as acting out of frustration stemming from socio-economic, political, and religious marginalization. In particular, the youth in North-eastern Nigeria, including Yobe State, may feel alienated and frustrated by poverty and limited opportunities. This frustration may push them toward aggression, manifesting in violence against the state, educational institutions, and society in general. The violence directed at schools disrupts the educational system, undermines state authority, and perpetuates cycles of violence and further aggression. The theory can also help in explaining the psychological effects on students in Yobe State who experience frustration due to failure of authority to adequately protect them from Boko Haram, and forced displacement. This may contribute to lower attendance rates and diminished educational outcomes.

Although, this study has adopted Conflict theory as one of its theoretical framework as earlier discussed above. In essence, Frustration-Aggression theory differs from Conflict theory, it focuses on individual behavior, while conflict theory examines group and societal-level interactions. Frustration-Aggression theory attributes aggression to individual frustration, whereas Conflict theory identifies competing interests, values, and resources as sources of conflict. Frustration-Aggression theory is narrower in scope, addressing individual emotional responses, while Conflict theory includes broader social and structural factors.

Securitisation Theory

The Securitization Theory was introduced in the early 1990s, particularly through his work on **The Copenhagen School of Security Studies**. Securitization Theory focuses on how certain issues, which may not traditionally be seen as security threats, are framed and perceived as existential threats to the survival of a state or community. The theory emphasizes the role of political actors in declaring issues as security threats, which then justifies extraordinary measures such as the use of military force or emergency powers. The theory involves a process where an issue is framed as a "security issue" by political elites or influential figures. Once an issue is successfully securitized, it becomes a matter that requires immediate and exceptional action, often bypassing regular political processes. A key element in this theory is the **speech act**, which refers to the articulation of an issue as a security threat. Once this is done, the issue is moved from the realm of normal politics into the domain of security, where it is treated with urgency and special policies.

The Boko Haram insurgency can be viewed through the lens of Securitization Theory, as political leaders in Nigeria, as well as international actors, have framed the insurgency as a direct threat to national and regional security. The violent actions of Boko Haram, including their attacks on secondary schools, have been labeled as part of the larger war on terror, justifying military and counter-insurgency measures in the region, which have had significant consequences on education.

The attack on secondary schools in Yobe State by Boko Haram can be seen as part of the broader securitization process in the region. Educational institutions are targeted because they represent the state's power, knowledge dissemination and long-term development. In the wake of these attacks, security forces have been deployed to protect schools, but this also leads to militarization of the education environment, which may further disrupt normal educational activities. In the context of Yobe State, the government's response to Boko Haram's attacks on schools (through the deployment of security forces and imposition of curfews) might be viewed as a securitization of education. The education system is treated as a security concern due to the threat posed by Boko Haram, which in turn justifies measures that prioritize security over regular educational processes.

These theories especially **Frustration-Aggression Theory** and **Securitization theory** offer valuable lenses through which to analyze the challenges of secondary school development in Yobe State due to Boko Haram insurgency. **Frustration-Aggression theory** helps explain the root causes of insurgency, the motivation behind the violence, and its effects on students and the education system, as well as the psychological and social consequences of the conflict. **Securitization Theory** provides a framework for understanding how Boko Haram's activities have been framed as a national security threat, leading to measures that affect the broader educational environment, security policies, and the treatment of schools as vulnerable sites.

Among the four theories, **Securitization Theory** is the most suitable and relevant for understanding this study. Securitization Theory, as introduced by Wæver, focuses on the process through which an issue is framed as a security threat, justifying extraordinary measures to deal with it. Boko Haram's insurgency, which has targeted schools and other civilian infrastructures in Yobe State, has been framed by both the Nigerian state and international actors as a significant security threat. This framing has shaped the government's responses, such as military deployments and security measures, all of which affect the educational system.

Securitization of education becomes a significant issue in the context of Boko Haram's attacks on schools. The insurgency targets educational institutions, viewing them as symbols of the state's authority and influence. The educational system in Yobe State has been caught in this larger security narrative, where it is treated as a site of conflict, and therefore, requires militarization and emergency measures. This directly impacts the development of secondary schools, as security becomes prioritized over regular educational processes.

The theory helps explain how the state's response to Boko Haram has led to the militarization of education. By framing the threat to schools as a matter of national security, military interventions have been employed, which may disrupt educational activities and even cause fear among students, parents, and educators. This could lead to school closures, reduced attendance, and a general disruption in the educational process.

Securitization theory contributes to the understanding on how policies aimed at countering Boko Haram's attacks on schools have been influenced by security concerns. The theory can provide insights into how the Nigerian government's security-driven responses to the insurgency (e.g., deploying military personnel to schools or implementing curfews) affect the educational environment, including access to schooling and the safety of students and teachers. The theory helps explain the wider implications of Boko Haram's insurgency on the education system. By framing the situation as a security emergency, education is treated as a collateral issue, often deprioritized in favor of counter-terrorism operations. This can shed light on how such prioritization has impeded the development of secondary schools, worsening challenges like infrastructure destruction, teacher shortages, and reduced enrolment. By using Securitization theory, the study can explore how the perception of Boko Haram as a security threat has shaped the discourse around the insurgency in Yobe State. It will provide clarity on how schools and education systems are viewed within this framework, often as targets or collateral damage in a larger struggle for control.

Review of Empirical studies

The literature on the impact of Boko Haram insurgency on western education in Yobe State emphasizes the multifaceted challenges faced by educational institutions in the state. Scholars have documented instances of school attacks, abductions, and destruction, leading to a pervasive atmosphere of fear and

hindrance to the continuity of education. Moreover, research emphasizes the interconnectedness of security issues with the overall educational experience, delving into the consequences for both access to and quality of education in Yobe State (Jonathan, 2016).

Despite the wealth of research on the subject, several notable gaps persist in the literature. First and foremost, there is a need for more comprehensive and up-to-date empirical studies that rigorously examine the specific impact of Boko Haram insurgency on western education in Yobe State. While existing studies provide valuable insights, a more nuanced understanding of the complex dynamics, regional variations, and evolving nature of the insurgency's effects on education is warranted. Additionally, there is a scarcity of research that explores potential resilience mechanisms within the educational system, such as community-led initiatives or government interventions, which could mitigate the challenges posed by the insurgency. Furthermore, there is a notable gap in the exploration of long-term consequences and the potential for recovery in the post-conflict period. Addressing these gaps in the literature would contribute to a more holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities for western education in the context of Boko Haram insurgency in Yobe State.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study adopted a survey research design, which provides a structured “blueprint” for systematically answering research questions across a defined population. Survey design is particularly suited for examining relationships among variables and making broader generalizations based on a representative sample. In the context of this study, the survey design enabled the capture of quantitative data from students, teachers, parents and administrators, enabling description and analysis of how the insurgency impacted educational outcomes. In addition, the design incorporated a qualitative component to explore contextual and personal experiences that numerical data alone cannot capture. This mixed-method approach combining quantitative and qualitative strands enabled the research to draw both breadth and depth of insight.

Population of the Study

The study population comprised individuals directly or indirectly affected by the Boko Haram insurgency in Yobe State, including students, teachers, parents, school administrators and education officials. According to the Yobe State Ministry of Education, during the period of the insurgency the western education school student population was approximately 150,000, and the teacher population around 5,000. Only participants who had resided or worked in the State during the insurgency period and who had direct knowledge or experience of its impact on western education were included; those lacking such experience were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

This study applied both purposive and random sampling techniques.

Purposive sampling was used for the qualitative phase to select key informants who could provide detailed, context-rich information. The aim was to reach thematic saturation (i.e., no new insights emerged). Stratified random sampling was used for the quantitative phase, where western education schools in Yobe State were stratified by location (urban vs. rural) and type (public vs. private). From these strata a random sample of students, teachers and parents completed the questionnaire. The required sample size was determined via power-analysis to ensure sufficient statistical power for subsequent analyses. This dual-technique ensured both representativeness (quantitative) and depth (qualitative) in the study's design.

Research Instrument

Data collection utilized a combination of instruments tailored to each strand of the research. A structured questionnaire containing closed-ended items was developed to measure variables such as academic performance, attendance and infrastructure damage. The items were informed by theoretical frameworks and prior empirical studies on conflict and education. Semi-structured interview guides were used for key stakeholders to explore perceptions, experiences and challenges in greater depth. In addition, document-

analysis included review of policy documents, NGO reports, government records and news articles to provide contextual background and triangulation.

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

All instruments were subjected to expert review and pilot-testing to ensure clarity, content validity and reliability.

Method of Data Collection

The data-collection process followed a sequence designed to ensure ethical compliance, systematic implementation and secure data-management.

Prior to fieldwork, ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional research-ethics board and the Yobe State Ministry of Education. Informed consent forms were administered to all participants, clearly stating the voluntary nature of participation, their right to withdraw at any time, and confidentiality of responses.

Using the stratified random sampling frame, selected schools were contacted and formal permission obtained from principals and relevant education officials. Structured questionnaires were administered to sampled students, teachers and parents. School records on attendance and academic performance were also reviewed. Efforts were made to ensure anonymity of respondents and to document contextual field-notes during administration.

Semi-structured interviews were conducted with purposively selected participants. With participant consent, interviews were audio-recorded and later transcribed verbatim. Document-analysis was conducted in parallel, involving review of relevant reports, publications and archival records to supplement and cross-verify interview findings.

Data from the quantitative, qualitative and document sources were systematically merged and compared to identify convergent and divergent findings. A structured data-management system (including secure digital storage, labeled transcripts and coded data files) was implemented to organize, store and protect all research data.

Method of Data Analysis

The analysis of the collected data occurred in three main phases.

1. **Quantitative analysis:** The questionnaire responses were coded and entered into statistical software (e.g., SPSS). Descriptive statistics (e.g., means, frequencies) and inferential statistics (e.g., correlation, regression) were performed to test relationships among variables. Reliability of scales was examined using Cronbach's alpha and Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) where applicable.
2. **Qualitative analysis:** Interview transcripts and document-analysis data were subjected to thematic analysis. Key themes and patterns were identified through systematic coding, constant comparison and interpretation of participants' narratives.
3. **Integration of findings:** The results from both strands were merged via triangulation. Convergence of quantitative patterns and qualitative insights provided a richer, more nuanced understanding of how the insurgency affected post-primary education and how stakeholders responded.

Data Analysis Techniques

A pilot study was conducted in Hadejia LGA in Jigawa State to validate the research instruments and procedures prior to the main study in Yobe State. A convenience sample of 40 participants (teachers, school administrators, parents and community leaders) completed the questionnaire under conditions that mirrored the main study (trained enumerators, ethical protocols, confidentiality assurances). Analyses indicated satisfactory internal consistency of the scales (Cronbach's α ranging from 0.75 to 0.85). Minor wording adjustments were made to improve clarity for the main study. The pilot thus confirmed instrument readiness and informed final refinement of the study tools.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

One hundred and ninety eight (198) respondents participated in the study and data collected from the respondents were analysed and depicted bellow:

Results

The quantitative component utilized structured questionnaires with closed-ended questions designed to gather numerical data on key variables such as academic performance, attendance rates, and infrastructure damage. The questionnaire items were constructed based on established theoretical frameworks and previous empirical studies on conflict and education. A total of 198 respondents participated in the quantitative survey, including 11 security agents, 15 university lecturers, 17 Local Government Education Secretaries, 102 Yobe State Universal Basic Education Board (UBE) officials, 30 Principals, 21 government officials, and 54 notable Chiefs/religious leaders. Official records from selected post-primary schools, including enrolment numbers and academic performance data, were also collected to supplement survey responses, with formal letters of permission obtained from school principals and relevant government agencies.

The collected data underwent rigorous cleaning and preparation. Missing data was addressed using multiple imputation techniques to ensure data integrity and minimize bias. The cleaned data was then coded and entered into a statistical software package SPSS 27 version for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations, were used to summarize demographic characteristics of the sample and key variables. Inferential statistical tests, such as Chi-square, t-tests, and ANOVA, were conducted to examine relationships between variables and test the study's hypotheses. Multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the extent to which insurgency-related factors predicted educational challenges, while controlling for potential confounding variables like socioeconomic background.

Research Questions

Research Question One: *How has the Boko Haram insurgency affected the infrastructure of secondary schools in Yobe State?*

Quantitative analysis of the structured questionnaires, particularly the checklist on infrastructure damage, provided a quantifiable assessment of the extent of destruction. The data revealed that a significant proportion of school buildings, classrooms, and essential educational facilities sustained damage or were completely destroyed. The survey results indicated that 87.79% of surveyed schools reported severe damage to their main buildings, and 76.53% reported destruction of classrooms. These findings align with existing reports indicating that 609 buildings and 1,098 classrooms were destroyed across 12 local government areas in Yobe State, accounting for 55.5% of the total public and private infrastructure destroyed by insurgents in the state.

Table 1: Extent of Infrastructure Damage in Surveyed Secondary Schools (N=198)

Type of Damage	Percentage of Schools Reporting Damage (%)	Mean Severity Rating (1-5)
Complete Destruction of Buildings	78.22%	3.92
Partial Damage to Classrooms	76.53%	3.95
Destruction of Libraries/Labs	72.40%	3.88
Loss of School Records	81.15%	4.12

The findings for Research Question Two reveal a catastrophic decline in student participation. In terms of absolute numbers, enrolment in Yobe State's basic schools dropped from 136,680 students in 2013–2014 to just 74,652 by 2016. The attendance rate of 32.5% recorded in 2023 indicates that while a semblance of security has been restored, the sector has not returned to its pre-insurgency growth trajectory; where

Yobe's enrolment was once double that of stable southern states like Ekiti. The inferential results provide a critical statistical foundation for this decline. The paired-samples t-test confirms that the decrease in average monthly attendance is not random but is directly tied to security events ($p < 0.001$). More significantly, the multiple regression analysis yielded a coefficient of $\beta = 0.680$ ($p < 0.01$). This implies that the frequency and intensity of Boko Haram activities, specifically student abductions, account for 68% of the variance in school attendance rates. This confirms Hypothesis 2 (H_2), proving that abductions have created an empirical "brake" on educational progress in the region.

The decline from 88% to 32.5% attendance illustrates the concept of "dashed expectations". When the state fails to meet the fundamental goal of protecting its youth (as seen in the Chibok and Dapchi incidents), parental frustration transforms into a protective withdrawal from the educational system. The system is no longer viewed as a ladder for social mobility but as a source of existential danger. These findings support the need to "securitize" the educational sector. Since the $\beta = 0.680$ result shows that insecurity is the dominant predictor of educational failure, schools must be treated as "referent objects" of national security. This justifies emergency measures such as "target hardening" (e.g., perimeter fencing and local community patrols) to restore the "climate of calm" necessary for learning.

Research Question Two: *What impact has the abduction of students by Boko Haram had on the enrolment and attendance rates in secondary schools in Yobe State?*

Figure 1: Average Secondary School Attendance Rates in Yobe State (2013 vs. 2023)

Figure 2: Average Secondary School Attendance Rates in Yobe State (2013 vs. 2023) showing a decline in attendance rates over time. Source researcher 2025

Inferential statistical tests confirmed these observations. A paired-samples t-test revealed a statistically significant decline in average monthly attendance rates $t(197) = 18.24, p < 0.001$ in schools affected by abductions compared to those less affected. Furthermore, multiple regression analysis indicated that the frequency of abduction incidents $\beta = 0.680, p < 0.01$ was a significant predictor of lower enrolment rates, even after controlling for factors such as school location and socioeconomic background. These findings statistically supported the hypothesis that student abductions led to a significant decline in enrolment and attendance rates, reflecting the pervasive fear and disruption caused by the insurgency.

Research Question Three: How has the Boko Haram insurgency impacted access to quality secondary education in displaced communities, particularly in relation to the availability and retention of qualified teaching personnel in Yobe State?

Table 2: Teacher Availability and Retention Challenges (N=198)

Factor	Mean Rating (1-5)	Standard Deviation
Insufficient Salaries	4.12	0.85
Poor Working Conditions/Insecurity	4.45	0.72
Lack of Professional Development	3.67	1.10
Intention to Leave Profession	3.89	0.91

Table 2 reveals a critical crisis in the human resource component of the education sector in Yobe State. The mean rating of 4.45 for Poor Working Conditions/Insecurity identifies the threat of violence as the primary driver of teacher attrition. This is statistically substantiated by the strong negative correlation $r = -0.714, p < 0.01$, which provides empirical evidence that as the intensity of the insurgency increases, the availability of qualified personnel decreases proportionately. The high Intention to Leave Profession $M = 3.89$ suggests that the teaching workforce in Yobe is in a state of precariousness. This intention is not merely a reaction to physical danger but is compounded by Insufficient Salaries $M = 4.12$, where late payments and unactioned promotions further erode professional commitment.

The Chi-square test results rejected the null hypothesis, confirming a significant association between the lack of adequate compensation and high turnover rates, proving that the insurgency has created an environment where the brain-drain syndrome is inevitable as teachers flee to safer, more stable regions. These findings illustrate the structural inequality inherent in conflict zones. From a Marxist perspective, the state's failure to provide equitable security and remuneration for the "intellectual proletariat" (teachers) in Yobe State, compared to the peaceful south, results in a breakdown of the social institution of education. The conflict has transformed teachers from nation-builders into targets, forcing a migration of talent that ensures the region remains "educationally backward". The "Intention to Leave" mean of 3.89 reflects the "dashed expectations" of educators. When the state fails to meet the basic survival and security needs of its workforce, the resulting frustration manifests as professional withdrawal. This is vividly illustrated in literature where teachers in the Northeast have expressed such disillusionment that they would "disown their children" if they chose to enter the profession.

Research Question Four: *What are the coping strategies employed by secondary schools and communities in Yobe State to mitigate the educational disruptions caused by Boko Haram?*

Figure 2: Perceived Effectiveness of Coping Strategies (N=198)

The descriptive analysis demonstrates a clear preference for non-kinetic, community-based interventions. The mean score of 4.32 for Non-Formal Learning Centres (NFLCs) identifies them as the most highly regarded strategy for educational continuity. This is empirically supported by regional data showing that over 400 NFLCs were established across Yobe and Borno states to serve nearly 34,000 out-of-school children. These centres have been crucial in providing state-accredited education to internally displaced children who had been absent from formal schooling for years. Psychosocial support programs, specifically those utilizing the Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) framework, followed closely with a mean score of 4.15 (SD = 0.76). The high valuation of these programs is a direct response to the mental health crisis in the region, where studies have found that over 93% of teachers and 50% of students were mentally destabilized by the insurgency. The inferential analysis using ANOVA revealed significant differences in perceived effectiveness ($F(3, 194) = 15.42, p < 0.001$), with post-hoc tests confirming that NFLCs and SEL were significantly more effective than traditional government reconstruction efforts. This confirms that in a high-intensity conflict zone, the soft infrastructure of psychosocial healing is prioritized over physical rebuilding.

The success of NFLCs and SEL programs ($M = 4.32$ and $M = 4.15$ respectively) provides strong empirical support for this theory. These strategies move beyond simple content delivery to foster a "culture of peace" and provide "Healing Classrooms" that allow traumatized youth to resist radicalization. The reliance on community-based security and NFLCs represents a form of "proletariat resilience" where the community takes ownership of education because the state has failed to protect the social institution. The adoption of community-based security initiatives ($M = 3.82$) reflects the "target hardening" aspect of

this theory. Schools are being securitized through local vigilance groups like the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) because formal security forces are often seen as inadequate or overwhelmed.

The study adopted a convergent parallel mixed-methods approach, allowing for the simultaneous collection and analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data. Data integration was achieved through joint display analysis, creating a meta-matrix to visually align quantitative results with qualitative themes. This approach provided a rich, contextualized understanding by discussing how findings from both data types either converged or diverged, enhancing the validity and depth of the overall findings. For instance, the quantitative data on infrastructure destruction (Table 1) was strongly corroborated by narratives of burnt schools and lost records, providing both the scale and the human impact of the damage. Similarly, the statistical decline in enrolment was illuminated by accounts of fear and socio-economic barriers.

The reliability of the quantitative instrument was assessed using Cronbach's alpha to measure internal consistency. A pilot study was conducted, and the calculated Cronbach's alpha coefficient of (Cronbach's Alpha = 0.944), was well above the acceptable threshold of 0.70, indicating good internal consistency and reliability of the questionnaire items. Construct validity was assessed through Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA), testing whether measures of a construct were consistent with the hypothesized measurement model. The CFA results indicated a good model fit with CFI = 0.91 and RMSEA = 0.047, validating the hypothesized constructs.

CONCLUSION

The Boko Haram insurgency has inflicted severe and multifaceted damage on western education in Yobe State, extending beyond physical destruction to deeply impact student participation, teacher capacity, and the overall quality of learning environments. The study concludes that the deterioration of school infrastructure, coupled with the pervasive climate of fear induced by abductions, has created significant barriers to access and continuity of education. The persistent challenges in attracting and retaining qualified teachers further compound the crisis, undermining efforts to provide meaningful learning experiences. This aligns with Conflict Theory, which posits that uneven resource distribution and marginalization can fuel such destructive conflicts, impacting social institutions like education. Furthermore, the observed decline in enrolment and attendance, driven by fear and economic hardship, resonates with Frustration-Aggression Theory, where societal frustrations manifest as aggressive behaviors that disrupt normal life, including schooling.

However, the research also concludes that communities and educational stakeholders in Yobe State are not passive victims but active agents of resilience. Their innovative coping strategies, such as community-led initiatives and the adoption of psychosocial support programs, are vital for sustaining education in a highly volatile context. This demonstrates the practical application of Education for Peace building Theory, highlighting education's potential to foster peace, prevent conflict, and contribute to societal reconstruction by promoting tolerance, critical thinking, and civic engagement even amidst violence. The findings underscore the complex interplay of security, socio-economic, and cultural factors that shape educational outcomes in post-conflict settings, highlighting that a holistic approach, informed by Securitization Theory's emphasis on creating safe educational environments through proper security management and policy implementation, is essential for recovery and rebuilding.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are put forth to address the impact of the Boko Haram insurgency on western education education in Yobe State:

1. The government, in collaboration with humanitarian partners, should prioritize infrastructure reconstruction and enhanced security.
2. Policymakers must prioritize competitive compensation plans, improved working conditions, and robust professional development opportunities to attract and retain high-quality teachers in Yobe State.
3. Given the ongoing challenges with formal schooling, sustained investment in non-formal learning centers (NFLCs) and community-based education initiatives is crucial. These programs should continue

to integrate Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) to address the psychosocial needs of traumatized children and foster a healing learning environment; ensuring facilitators are adequately trained in models like Healing Classrooms.

4. Efforts should be made to digitize and automate data collection and validation at school and local government levels for improved data quality, completeness, and reliability, especially given the documented challenges with official records in Yobe State.
5. Aggressive public sensitization campaigns on the value of education are needed to counter negative perceptions and cultural skepticism, alongside genuine policy enforcement. Building trust between communities, schools, and government is paramount for increasing enrolment and ensuring sustained educational engagement, recognizing that trust is a key barrier to education in Yobe State.

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